

EXTENDED CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS POST-TRAINED WITH FACTORED STATISTICAL MACHINE

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Abstract: This paper investigate the potential of coupling two machine translation research approaches while taking full advantage of each method, namely, the deterministic (neuronal) and probabilistic (statistical) approaches, in order to address three main problems occurring in MT, that is, language pairs having grammatical structure and word order that differs drastically, data sparseness and the number of out of vocabulary (OOV) words generated. Additionally, we integrated word-level linguistic features (Part-of- Speech with compounds, lemmatization and/or word class) so as to decrease the number of unknown words while significantly increasing the vocabulary coverage. We combined a fully-factored ConvS2S and a factored PB-SMT where, the pre-translated training data generated using the NMT system is employed to build the SMT system, parallelly, tuning parameters using the pre-translated development set. Finally, the desired results where produced by operating in the post-translation step the SMT system to re-decode the pre-translated test set. Experiments are performed on comparisons between stand-alone vs. our hybrid MT models where our model outperforms the strong MTs state-of-the-art by over 3.88 %BLEU, 3.08 %BLEU and 3.52 %BLEU, on the WMT'16 English-Romanian, WMT'14 English-German and WMT'14 English-French translation tasks, respectively, and hybrid recurrent vs. hybrid ConvS2S MT models where our model outperforms the strong HMTs state-of-the-art by over 3.95 %BLEU and 5.68 %BLEU on the Japanese-English and Chinese-English test sets, respectively.

Keywords: Neural Networks; Extended ; Convolutional; Post;

I. INTRODUCTION

Although the adequacy of statistical machine translations (SMT) has been surpassed or rivalled by the fluency of the neural machine translations models [1],[2],[3],[4],[5], which have achieved the state of the art in machine translation due to their fundamental design, NMT models are constraint by the need for the observation of many examples of a word till the reliability of its embedding (input representation) and the computational necessity that they use a fixed modest-size vocabulary to few tens of thousands of words which most often leads to coverage issues and the loss of rare words identity, thus performs poorly in translating infrequent or unseen words, by so doing NMT models still face major problems when dealing with morphologically-rich and/or low resource languages, which are characterized by their high lexical sparseness, due to the occurrence of unseen word forms (commonly known as uncommon and rare words) in source texts during training, caused by their lexical productivity and morphological variation.

Thus, novel target word forms are required to be generated; leading to huge input/output vocabularies, which can partially mitigate these issues, but to the serious detriment of the stability during the rare or unseen words embedding's computation, and also, complexity issues when operating with large softmax layers. Accordingly, sentences containing only common words tend to be translated better than those containing rare words [2],[3]. However, due to the deficiencies encountered by NMT systems when operating on morphologically-rich and/or low resource languages such as limited vocabulary size and computational complexity, which leads to meaningless translations, much research work has been done in order to improve translation performance by establishing a hybrid paradigm which combines NMT and SMT [6],[7],[8],[9], so as to fully take advantage of each system's strength. The hybrid paradigm points out its importance while dealing with the translations having a totally different meaning as compared to their source sentences, generated by the NMT systems, due to their weak translation modelling but strong language modelling, by integrating a phrase based-SMT system in a cascaded manner, through which the source sentences adequacy is proficiently reflected by means of their 'hard word alignment'. Intuitively, if we operate by considering the fluent but wrong translations generated as another language and perform a hard word alignment, then the original meaning of source sentences can perhaps be restored to some extent using PB-SMT. More to that, due to the fact that most neural models encounter the problem of handling out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens that appear in the test set by relying on words as their basic units, generally a special UNK token is assigned to those words, which arrives at the expense of modelling accuracy, and if we maintain kept in the translations the source-side out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words produced by the NMT, then we can fully take advantage of the PB-SMT potentialities to translate and realign them.

Equally, in order to overcome the data sparseness problem caused by limited in-domain training data, we integrated additional rich information of words in particular morphological and syntactic features, through factors. Moreover, due to the integration of additional features (factors) our HMT model converges faster, and well addresses the optimization problem in factored n-gram language models by simultaneously interpolating all possible factors and considering the entire history. This paper is organized as follows: We discuss the factorization process with the integration of compounds in Section 2. In Section 3, we describe the convolutional operation with the incorporation of linguistic factors in detail. Section 4 detail our proposed neural hybrid MT framework. Section 5 discusses about the experimental setup. In Section 6, the results and analysis of two sets of experiments, that is, standalone vs. our hybrid MT models and hybrid recurrent vs. hybrid ConvS2S MT models, tasks are reported measured by their BLEU score. Finally, in Section 7 we summarize our findings and outline future plans.

II. FACTORIZATION AND WORD COMPOUNDING INTEGRATION

In this work we propose an approach using factored representations of words, where, rather than representing words as indices in the neural network, we instead represent them as tuples of indices $w = (f_1, \dots, f_D)$, having D as the number of different factors used to describe the word. These factors are referring to the linguistic annotation at word level, which may be the automatic learned classes, Part of Speech (POS), and even word itself [10] or other information about the word such as dependency information and syntactic information, retrieved from a given word using TreeTagger [11] and integrating it as a vector into a translation system. Furthermore, different types of factors can be used for the input and the output of the neural network, and equally, has shown to be very successful on n-gram language models based on POS tags in phrase-based machine translation when dealing with morphologically rich languages. Machine translation from one morphological rich language to another has been a tedious task especially when aiming at reducing the rate Out-Of-Vocabulary (OOV) occurrences and the amount of bilingual data while not having enough required morphological information on the source and/or target side, thus, the call for factored models is highly recommended and therefore majorly used.

We generate the probabilities $P_1, \dots, P_D$ for every sentence by training the individual models for all factors $1, \dots, D$ and use these probabilities as features for example necessary for the re-scoring of the phrase-based MT system. Proven therefor to be helpful in considering all factors of the word in the input, the different output factors/features are predicted by jointly training the models (Collobert et al., 2011), which would jointly require a modification of the output layer of the neural network model. We could either only use as feature in the log-linear combination the joint probability $P = \prod_{d=1}^D P_d$, where P_d is one word factor with $d \in \{1, \dots, D\}$. Or in addition, we could use as features both the joint probability and the individual probabilities P_d .

A. Compound splitting

Integrating word compounding in the pre-processing phase is pronounced to be highly productive and useful in order to have an exact target language word-form by adding extra morphological information to the linguistic/morphological factors of the source and target languages such as filler letters (example: -s, -en, -ien) or from the end of all but the last word remove letters (example: -en, -n) of the compound [13], since it increases the vocabulary size and deals with sparse data problems [14],[15],[16].

Operating at the level of POS tag, compounding produces refined and minimized part-of-speech tag obtained from a TreeTagger using a dependency parser to compute the frequencies of, and integrate morphological information including gender, number, case, verbs, person for nouns, definiteness, pronouns, determiners and adjectives, provided that both tools agreed on the POS-tag. In case of disagreement, we elected the POS-tags from the TreeTagger. [14] proposed an adjusted version of the corpus-based method on which we rely, where known words from the corpus are produced from each splitted adjective and noun, and in the fear of giving rise to errors during partial translation proper names are not splitted, while permitting filler additions and truncations. Equally, due to the fact that base forms are often contained in the compound parts, word frequencies are computed using both lemmas and surface forms. More to that, rather than using the geometric mean of the frequencies of its parts, the value of the highest arithmetic mean is instead used to obtain more splits. We set the minimum words length to be split ≥ 7 and particularly restricted to ≤ 2 the number of parts for adjectives, with each compound parts limited to 4 characters and all parts but the last marked with the symbol # so as to be computed as separate words. Based on the compounds last word's POS we assigned special POS tags to split words parts, while attributing the same POS to both the full word and the last part. Furthermore, based on the same algorithm, different POS-tags are assigned to parts of a splitted word that contained hyphens, with hyphens conserved at the end of all but the last part. In the pre-processing step for training and translation of both the neural network framework and the Phrase-based statistical machine framework, factorization integrating compound splitting was operated.

B. Compound merging

The merging operation is performed on splitted compounds during the translation into the morphologically rich language through a post-processing step at the outputs of both the neural network framework and the Phrase-based statistical machine framework based on POS. From that, if a word possesses a compound-POS and the following word possesses a matching POS, they are merged. Alternatively, coordinate compounds are allowed where, in case of incompatibility with the next POS a hyphen is added to the word. We used the strength of the merging algorithm proposed by [16] based on [15], where, coordinated compounds can be handled and unseen compounds merged.

III. CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK INCORPORATION WITH LINGUISTIC FACTORS

Compared to recurrent layers, by stacking several layers on each other the CNN effective context size can easily be altered, although the fixed size context representations created. Thus, allowing the modelling of the maximum length of dependencies to be incisively controlled. Also, shorter paths to capture long-range dependencies are provided due to their hierarchical structure i.e. for kernels of width k , by applying only $O(n/k)$ convolutional operations feature representation capturing relationships within a window of n words can be obtained, meanwhile the chain structure which are modelled by recurrent neural networks apply a linear number $O(n)$ recurrent operations to capture feature representations. More to that, parallelization is allowed over the entire sequence since CNN are independent of the previous time step computations. Our principal innovation over the standard convolutional neural networks (CNN) architecture proposed by [17] equipped with residual connections [18], gated linear units [19] and attention in every decoder layer [20], is that we extended it by expressing the encoder input and decoder output as a combination of features as suggested [21],[22]. Our generalized model supports an arbitrary number of input features. Focusing in this paper on a number of well-known linguistic features, our investigation was to evaluate to which extent does providing linguistic features to both encoder and decoder of the CNN paradigm improves the translation quality when dealing with morphologically richer languages.

In considering that we have N training parallel sentences from the training data and L layers of annotations for linguistic factors, with $\left\{ \left[x^{(n,l)}, y^{(n,l)} \right]_{l=0}^L \right\}_{n=1}^N$, where in layer zero the n -th sentence pair word sequence is denoted by $x^{(n,0)}$ with its length denoted by $|x^{(n)}|$, $\left\{ x^{(n,l)} \right\}_{l=1}^L$ denoting its L layers of annotation and $y^{(n,l)}$ denotes the target sentence. As such, we look up separate embedding vectors for each feature and concatenate them, after which the concatenated vectors matches the total embedding size, while maintaining the internal structure of the sequence to sequence architecture that is entirely convolutional. Thus, it is according to this setting that we extended our standard encoder-decoder based CNN architecture, which operates as follows: Input elements $x = (x_1, \dots, x_s)$ are embedded in a distributional vector space as $w = (w_1, \dots, w_s)$, with $w_j \in \mathbb{R}^f$ being a column in an embedding matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times f}$. And instead of equipping our model by embedding absolute position of the input elements, we rather implemented a precise relative positional embedding as proposed [23], which we precise not been useful beyond a certain distance, as such, we clipped the maximum distance so as for the model to be able to generalize to sequence lengths not seen during training. Sharing a simple block composed of a non-linearity preceded by a one dimensional convolution, which based on a fixed number of input elements compute intermediate states, the encoder network output is denoted as $z^l = (z_1^l, \dots, z_s^l)$ and the decoder network output is denoted as $h^l = (h_1^l, \dots, h_s^l)$, while we refer layers and blocks interchangeably.

Information over k input elements is contained in each resulting state h_i^l given a decoder network which contains a kernel width k and a single block. Also, the number of input elements represented in a state can be increased by stacking several blocks on top of each other. Each convolution kernel takes as input $X \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times d}$ where the k input elements are concatenated and embedded in d dimensions, and is parameterized as $W \in \mathbb{R}^{2d \times kd}$, $b_w \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$, after which it performs their mapping to a single output element $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$; operating subsequent layers over the previous layer k output elements. A simple gated linear mechanism according to [19] is implemented as non-linearity over the convolution output as;

$$Y = [A \ B] \in \mathbb{R}^{2d} \quad (1)$$

$$u([A \ B]) = A \otimes \sigma(B) \quad (2)$$

having as inputs to the non-linearity $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the point wise multiplication $\otimes$ and half the output size of Y as $u([A \ B]) \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Equally, from each convolution input to the output of the block we added residual connections [18].

$$h_i^l = u(W^l [h_{i-k/2}^{l-1}, \dots, h_{i+k/2}^{l-1}] + b_w^l) + h_i^{l-1} \quad (3)$$

We make sure that the input length is matched by the convolutional layers for the encoder networks by padding the input at each layer. Finally, the top decoder output h_i^l is transformed through a linear layer with weights W_o and bias b_o in order to compute the distribution over the T possible target elements y_{i+1} :

$$p(y_{i+1} | y_1, \dots, y_t, x) = \text{softmax}(W_o h_i^l + b_o) \in \mathbb{R}^T \quad (4)$$

We precise that, the state i attention α_{ij}^l at the decoder layer l and source element j is computed between the decoder state summary d_i^l and each output z_j^p as the dot-product of the last decoder block:

$$\alpha_{ij}^l = \frac{\exp(d_i^l \cdot z_j^p)}{\sum_{p=1}^P \exp(d_i^l \cdot z_j^p)} \quad (5)$$

$$d_i^l = W_d^l h_i^l + b_d^l + g_i \quad (6)$$

Where, g_i denotes the previous target element and i the current decoder state. And the conditional input to the decoder computed as;

$$c_i^l = \sum_{j=1}^P \alpha_{ij}^l (z_j^p + e_j) \quad (7)$$

A. Beam search integration with factors

In order to enrich the output and help the translation process we provided the grammatical and morphological information through factors, as we extended the decoder of our ConvS2S architecture in order to allow the system to simultaneously generate several output symbols. We focused on the generation of only two symbols for simplicity reasons; that is, the concatenation of the various factors that we considered and the lemma, while constricting the length of the factors sequence to be equal to that of the lemma sequence with each sequence of symbols ending with a generated $\langle \text{eos} \rangle$ (end-of-sequence) symbol, since the lemmas and factors are initially generated in a synchronous stream leading to sequences with different lengths. This is justified by the fact that lemmas are the symbols that bears sense and meaning of the final surface form (sequence of words). The MACAON toolkit was employed to perform the grammatical and morphological analysis, while taking into account the context [24].

As such, the next word in the sequence is generated by considering the previous word (feedback) taking into consideration its various outputs (features), in this case for the feedback model we concatenated the embeddings so as to get full benefit of both outputs using a non-linear operation, where W_{prev_w} denotes the trained weights, Prev_w computes the previous output y_{t-1} feedback, provided that the embeddings of the lemma y_{t-1}^L and factors y_{t-1}^F are generated at the previous time step:

$$\text{Prev}_w(y_{t-1}) = \tanh([y_{t-1}^L; y_{t-1}^F] \cdot W_{\text{prev}_w}) \quad (7)$$

We respect to this approach the beam search procedure has equally been extended therefor having one beam for lemmas and another one for factors. The cross product of the output spaces for each partial hypothesis was done considering the best lemma and factors hypotheses generated, therefor associating the hypothesis of each factor to that of each lemma, while keeping the k -best combination for each sample, where k denotes the beam size. Finally, the MACAON toolkit was once more exploited in order to obtain the word candidate provided that we have the lemma and some factors, and in situations where we had no factors found (such as is the case for name entities) the lemma was outputted by the system.

IV. CASCADED HYBRID FRAMEWORK OPERATION

Even though NMT generally produces more fluent translations than PB-SMT, they still face the challenge of producing translations where some source words are repeated while ignoring other words mistakenly [25], we believe this is initiated due to the lack of an explicit translation model making the whole framework of the NMT to be regarded as a language model, thus, generating meaningless translations (those totally different from the source sentence original meaning) [26]. Regarding the translation produced by the NMT (ConvS2S) as been a tertiary/intermediate language, we infer that to some extent we might alleviate the duplicated and meaningless translations by using henceforth a PB-SMT to build a translation model and perform word alignment.¹ We therefore propose a cascaded *ConvS2S* $\Rightarrow$ *PB-SMT* framework implemented as a factored multi-engine hybrid MT system, illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The Factored Hybrid MT framework

As first step in this pipeline, the initial factored training data is used to train the ConvS2S and generate pre-translations which act as tertiary/intermediate language obtained by translating the training data, the (devset) development set and the (testset) test set. As second step, the pre-translated training data and the pre-translated devset are used to respectively build a target-target PB-SMT and tune the parameters. And the final steps consist in decoding the pre-translated testset using the tuned PB-SMT system in order to generate the final output. While using the CNN to produce the pre-translations by translating the training data, devset and testset, an 'UNK' token is generated if in the source sentence there is an occurrence of OOV. In order to more simply and efficiently replace the 'UNK' token by the corresponding source word, we propose a novel technic known as the "labelled UNK replacement algorithm", which palliates the inadequacy faced by the UNK replacement algorithm proposed by [27] been inspired from [28], in which wrong replacements are performed if there eventually exist different word order between the source sentence and the target sentence. Algorithm 1 presents this technic. According to our algorithm, when traversing the translation if an 'UNK' token is encountered it is replaced with the corresponding source word (by referring to the key at that position), provided that there is no existence of the source word in the vocabulary.

Algorithm 1 Labelled UNK replacement by source words

Require: The translation e_1^{m1} with UNK tokens from the CNN.

With e as an array of key and value pairs where each key is a source word, and the value the corresponding translation or UNK token.

e.g: for the French sentence: "un chat noir" to translate in English, we may have the corresponding e below.

{un:a}	{noir:black}	{chat:UNK}	{eos:eos}
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Considering that we have the following sentence, the replacement will thus be done as:

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1: procedure LABELLED UNK REPLACEMENT
2:   for  $i = 1$  to  $m$  do
3:     if  $e_i.value == UNK$  then
4:        $e_i.value = e_i.key$ 
5:     end if
6:   end for
7: end procedure
  
```

Contrary to [29] who post-process these unknown words using a back-off dictionary, we performed the desired translation while considering more context by using a factored phrase based SMT system. In the factored PB-SMT, we employed the Moses toolkit [30] for training and decoding,² we used SRILM [31] for sequence models in order to train a 5-gram language model, and we used Giza++ [32] for word alignments creation, while for feature weights tuning we used the MERT (Minimum Error Rate Training) [33].

V. EXPERIMENTS

A. Datasets for Stand-Alone MT Frameworks

For the sake of fair comparison with the state-of-the-art ConvS2S for NLP (Natural Language Processing) [17], GNMT [34], ByteNet [35], and LSTM [36], three major translation tasks were considered.

WMT'16 English- Romanian. We use the same data and pre-processing as [17] based on [37], resulting in 2.8M sentence pairs for training, and we perform the evaluation on newstest2016.³

WMT'14 English- German. We equally use the same data as [17] conformed to [20], containing 4.5M sentence pairs for training, and we perform the evaluation on newstest2014.⁴

WMT'14 English- French. The full training set of 36M sentence pairs was exploited, with both sentences longer than 175 words and those whose pairs where the source/target length ratio exceeds 1.5 removed. We therefore obtained 35.5M sentence pairs for training and reported the results on newstest2014.

Due to the fact that, unknown words (OOV) cannot be generated by BPE systems as they are all encoded as BPE units [38], BLEU scores [39] cannot improve since incorrect words are sometimes generated during the production of the final word level translation. As such, we used 40K word units as vocabulary.

For early stopping and learning rate annealing, we use a small subset, which is about 0.5-1% of each training data set in all the setups which serves as validation set.

B. Datasets for Hybrid MT Frameworks

In the interest of implementing a fair comparison with the state-of-the-art in hybrid MT frameworks with reference to the *Factored NMT* → *SMT* pipeline [27], *SMT* → *NMT* pipeline [40], *NMT* – *Nematus* [41], and *PB* – *SMT* [42], we consider two major translation tasks conformed to the datasets below: Japanese-English. We exploit the JP–EN Scientific Paper Abstract Corpus (ASPEC-JE) first part (train-1) that contains 1M sentence pairs, while considering 1,790 and 1,812 sentence pairs for the development/validation and test set, respectively [43]. Chinese-English. We extracted from the LDC ZH–EN corpora 1.4M sentence pairs used as the training data, while considering NIST 2004 and NIST 2005 current sets having 1,597 and 1,082 sentences as the development/validation set and test set, respectively. For the Japanese-English translation direction each source-side sentence have only one reference in the validation and test sets, meanwhile the validation and test sets of the Chinese-English translation direction has for each Chinese sentence four references and only one reference for each English sentence.⁵

We use the KyTea [44] and ICTCLAS toolkit [45] in order to segment and tag the Japanese and Chinese data, respectively, so as to obtain the POS tags which were further more refined as we integrated compounds. Moreover, for comparison sake, we use “mkcls” to obtain word classes (WoC) of the training data, setting the number of classes to 50, while randomly allocating a class between (1, 50) to OOV words appearing the validation and test sets. The vocabulary size is set to 45K based on word encoded as translation units.

C. Optimization and Model Parameters

In the case of single models for fair comparison, we used embedding of size 512 and mini-batches of 64 sentences while restricting the maximum number of words for proper fitting in the GPU memory, unless otherwise stated. Nesterov's accelerated gradient [46] with a momentum value of 0.99 and gradients renormalize whenever their norm exceeds 0.1 [47], was used for training. A learning rate of 0.25 was used till no noticeable improvement in the validation perplexity which due to the cause was afterwards reduced after each epoch by an order of magnitude till it drops below 10^{-4} . Except for lookup tables, weight normalization is applied to all layers [48], with drop out [49]. Trained on a machine with 8 NVIDIA P100 GPUs, all models are implemented in Torch [50]. Similarly, in the case of hybrid models for fair comparison, we fixed the total embedding size to worth 600, and mini-batches of 80 sentences while restricting the maximum number of words to 60 and setting the beam size of all NMT systems to 5. Between epochs the training corpus is reshuffled, while exploiting the Adadelta optimizer [51] to train our models, after which through BLEU scores on every 5,000 mini-batches they are validated and saved after every 30,000 iterations.

D. Evaluation

The average results are reported over three runs of each model, differing at their initial random seed each. Through a beam search translations are generated, with the log-likelihood scores normalized by sentence length. A length normalization constant is tuned for the case of WMT'14 English-German on a separate development set (that is, newstest2015) and log-likelihoods normalize by $|y|^{\alpha}$ [34]. Unknown word replacement is performed for word-based models according to the "label unknown replacement algorithm" proposed in section 4, with reference to a pre-computed dictionary into which if no translation is found, the source word is simply copied. We point out that the word aligned training data from which the dictionaries were extracted are obtained with *fast_align* [52], from which a mapping is done between each source word and the target word it is aligned to, most frequently.

For the case of our hybrid MT model, the pre-translated training data and development set are only employed from the fully factored CNN system for factored PB-SMT engine training and tuning. Subsequently, using the fully factored ConvS2S the tuned factored PB-SMT system is engaged to re-decode the pre-translated test set.

Finally, for stand-alone systems, the case-sensitive tokenized BLEU is computed, except for WMT'16 English-Romanian where the de-tokenized BLEU is used so as to be comparable with both [17] and [37].⁶ And for the case of hybrid MT systems the case-insensitive BLEU scores are reported and through a bootstrap re-sampling significance test statistical significance is calculated [53], provided that, the various models are trained on non-reordered data.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Stand-Alone vs. our Hybrid MT models

We primarily evaluated our cascaded HMT model composed of a fully factored ConvS2S and factored PB-SMT on four translation tasks. We compared to the winning entry model [37] based on the language pair at WMT'16 [54] of the WMT'16 English-Romanian translation. Equally, we performed evaluations on both the word-based and BPE vocabularies of the state-of-the-art ConvS2S [17]. All the aforementioned models implements the [55] attention-based sequence to sequence represented in an encoder-decoder architecture.

Table 1 shows that our cascaded HMT model on the **WMT'16 English-Romanian** outperforms both the fully convolutional sequence to sequence model (ConvS2S) by 4.47 BLEU score on the word factored vocabulary and 3.88 BLEU score on the BPE vocabulary; equally, outperforms the WMT'16 winning entry for English-Romanian by 5.81 BLEU score with a BPE encoding. For the sake of fair comparison, we set this instance of our architecture to have 20 layers in both the encoder and decoder, exploiting kernels of width 3. For the WMT'14 English to German translation task we used the following prior work for comparison: an attention based four layer LSTM model [36] a character without attention based convolutional model proposed by ByteNet [35] set to operate the encoder and decoder with 30 layers each, an encoder-decoder architecture based on eight LSTM each proposed as GNMT by [34] quoting their results for a both a word-based and word-piece model [56], and the state-of-the-art ConvS2S represented by [17] on this dataset.⁷

The results reflected on the second set of experiments in Table 1 clearly shows that our cascaded HMT model on the **WMT'14 English to German** outperforms both the ConvS2S and word-piece based GNMT models by 3.08 and 3.64 BLEU scores, respectively.

For the sake of fair comparison, we set this instance of our architecture to have 15 layers in both the encoder and decoder each, basically having for the first ten layers 512 hidden units and gradually augmenting to three subsequent layers 768 hidden units, with the final two layers set to 2048 hidden units been just linear mappings with a single input, while exploiting kernels of width 3 and a batch size of 48. Finally, on the much larger **WMT'14 English-French** task we perform training and compare the result to the state-of-the-art ConvS2S [17] and of GNMT [34] both with and without reinforcement learning.

Thus, we improve over ConvS2S and GNMT in the same setting with a BLEU score average of 3.52 and 5.08 respectively. Why we also outperform the reinforcement learning (RL) model implemented in GNMT by 4.09 BLEU score. For simplicity reasons and for the sake of comparison, the same configuration as for WMT'14 English-German was used.

TABLE I- Experiments compared to previous works reported on WMT tasks. ConvS2S, GNMT and our HMT results are averaged over several runs.

WMT'16 English-Romanian	BLEU
Sennrich et al. (2016b) GRU (BPE 90K)	28.1
ConvS2S (Word 80K)	29.44
ConvS2S (BPE 40K)	30.03
ConvS2S⇒PBSMT (word 40K)	31.37
Fully Factored ConvS2S⇒Factored PBSMT (word 40K)	33.91
WMT'14 English-German	BLEU
Luong et al. (2015) LSTM (Word 50K)	20.9
Kalchbrenner et al. (2016) ByteNet (Char)	23.74
Wu et al. (2016) GNMT (Word 80K)	23.13
Wu et al. (2016) GNMT (Word pieces)	24.61
ConvS2S (BPE 40K)	25.17
ConvS2S⇒PBSMT (word 40K)	26.02
Fully Factored ConvS2S⇒Factored PBSMT (word 40K)	28.25
WMT'14 English-French	BLEU
Wu et al. (2016) GNMT (Word 80K)	37.91
Wu et al. (2016) GNMT (Word pieces)	38.94
Wu et al. (2016) GNMT (Word pieces) + RL	39.93
ConvS2S (BPE 40K)	40.50
ConvS2S⇒PBSMT (word 40K)	41.92
Fully Factored ConvS2S⇒Factored PBSMT (word 40K)	44.02

Our models produce translations that more accurately matches the length of the references as compared to the state-of-the-art, observed particularly on the large WMT'14 English-French dataset translation task, more to that, the rate of OOVs is significantly reduces with better translations produced when handling sparse and small datasets such as the WMT'14 English-German or WMT'16 English-Romanian, we infer this is due to the integration of factors in the entire HMT framework.

B. Hybrid Recurrent vs. Hybrid CNN models

According to the experiments performed on various previous cascaded HMT models reported in Table 2, we observe that:

TABLE III

Results based on PBSMT⇒NMT, NMT⇒PBSMT experiments for JP→EN and ZH→EN non-reordered translation tasks. Where “*”, “F”, “Ens”, and “FF”, indicates significantly better translation performance, factored models, ensembles models and fully factored models, respectively.

SYSTEM	JP-EN		ZH-EN	
	Validation	Test	Validation	Test
Koehn et al. (2003) PBSMT	18.25	17.64	33.13	29.24
Bahdanau et al. (2015) NMT	24.16	24.55	35.49	31.71
Niehuess et al. (2016) PBSMT⇒NMT	18.01	17.83	32.87	28.86
Du and Way (2017) NMT⇒PBSMT	25.33*	25.66*	36.58*	32.38*
F-NMT	25.08	25.17	37.42	33.15
Du and Way (2017) F-NMT⇒PBSMT	25.94*	26.08*	37.69*	33.39*
Ens-NMT	26.24	26.37	39.10	35.69
Ens-NMT⇒PBSMT	26.80*	26.94*	39.53*	35.98*
ConvS2S⇒PBSMT	27.92	28.01	40.79	38.04
FF- ConvS2S⇒F-PBSMT	30.47*	30.89*	44.82*	41.66*

JP-EN: the translation performance operated by the NMT⇒PBSMT is improved on the validation set and test set by 7.32 and 7.83 BLEU scores, respectively, compared to that operated by the PBSMT⇒NMT. Similarly, compared to the translation operated by the NMT⇒PBSMT, those produced by F-NMT⇒PBSMT are significantly better with an improvement of 0.86 and 0.42 BLEU scores on the validation and test sets, respectively.

While the translations produced by Ens-NMT⇒PBSMT outperforms those produce by F-NMT⇒PBSMT with an increase in BLEU score of 0.84 and 0.86 on the validation and test set, respectively. Finally, the translations generated by our proposed HMT consistently outperforms the state-of-the-art Ens-NMT⇒PBSMT with an increase in BLEU scores of 3.67 and 3.95 for the validation set and test set, respectively.

ZH-EN: the translation performance operated by the NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT is improved on the validation set and test set by 3.71 and 3.52 BLEU scores, respectively, compared to that operated by the PBSMT $\Rightarrow$ NMT. Similarly, compared to the translation operated by the NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT, those produced by F-NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT are significantly better with an improvement of 1.09 and 1.01 BLEU scores on the validation and test sets, respectively. While the translations produced by Ens-NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT outperforms those produce by F-NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT with an increase in BLEU score of 1.84 and 2.59 on the validation and test set, respectively. Finally, the translations generated by our proposed HMT consistently outperforms the state-of-the-art Ens-NMT $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT with an increase in BLEU scores of 5.29 and 5.68 for the validation set and test set, respectively.

We thus can conclude from our results that, our proposed FF-ConvS2S $\Rightarrow$ F-PBSMT pipeline is more feasible and effective than both the F- MT $\Rightarrow$ SMT and SMT $\Rightarrow$ NMT pipelines. In [8], the SMT $\Rightarrow$ NMT pipeline only performs better when integrating the source information into NMT, however, due to the concatenation of the pre-translated and source sentences as input to NMT, the computational complexity is increased. Meanwhile, our proposed HMT framework only uses source-side information once, that is, at the stage of ConvS2S training, and hence forth post process the data using only the generated pre-translations without the source information (except for the case of OOVs processing), thus keeping the framework simpler than the SMT $\Rightarrow$ NMT framework. More to that, in our proposed framework we observed a consistently decreased OOVs rate, enabling due to the test set larger vocabulary the post-processing PBSMT system to translate some of the OOVs appearing in this set. From that, we observed a significant reduction in OOVs rate in the final results of our proposed framework as compared to the stat-of-the-art, that is, from 3.57% to 1. 04%.

C. Aggregation studies

In this section, we explore how some light is shed through the salient behaviour of each individual architecture family which composes our hybrid framework, in order to evaluate the extent to which each contribute to the performance of our hybrid framework, and thus, have a better understanding on the relative usefulness, capabilities and/or limitations of each architecture family. We performed aggregation analysis and evaluate the performance changes on the non-reordered JP-EN translation tasks, while compare the changes in % BLEU scores on the test set and displaying the results in Table 3.

TABLE IIIV- Aggregation study of our proposed HMT model on JP-EN test set

SYSTEM	BLEU	Δ
ConvS2S $\Rightarrow$ PBSMT (Baseline)	28.01	
Baseline with F-ConvS2S	28.99	0.98 $\uparrow$
Baseline with FF-ConvS2S	29.61	1.60 $\uparrow$
Baseline with FF-ConvS2S + F-PBSM	30.89	2.88 $\uparrow$

The analysis of the changes reported in table 3, shows that when adding features on the input of the ConvS2S model constituting our baseline framework, we have a slight improvement in the BLEU score of 0.98. When implementing a fully factored neural network by integrating features at both the input and output levels of the ConvS2S model, we obtain a significant improvement in BLEU score of 1.60. And finally, the aggregation of our fully factored NM architecture with a factored phrase based SM architecture (features integrated on the input), gives a considerable improvement in BLEU score of 2.88.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a novel HMT framework cascaded as a Fully-Factored ConvS2S $\Rightarrow$ Factored SMT pipeline composed of linguistic features integrated at both the source language and target language of the ConvS2S model, linguistic features integrated only at the input side of the PB-SMT model while been implemented on the pre-translated language.

The linguistic features we considered where lemmatization, part-of-speech tagging (while integrating its various compounds) and eventually word classes on certain cases. Our experimental results when comparing our proposed HMT framework with stand-alone architectures clearly reveals a significant improvement in terms of % BLEU scores. More to that, an important reduction in OOV rate was observed, thanks to the integration of additional linguistic resources leading to the generation of new word forms.

As future work, we aim to explore the impact of the integration of a reinforcement learning method such as professor forcing [57]. Also, perform ablation/aggregation studies on the various features type in order to explore the effect of removing/integrating different feature kinds in both the NMT model and SMT model, therefore optimizing the model so as to consider lesser but more relevant features and produce greater impacts on the results. Finally, performing experiments on our model that sums the output of at least four experts such as in [58], and also, by summing multiple networks output such as the case of ensemble models, so as to obtain the best results out of our model.

VIII. CONFLICTS OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors whose names are listed above certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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